

IntegrateMind: A Multidisciplinary Journal

To Cite:

Taiwo K. Ojediran, Olujimi John. A., Durojaye V. and Emiola, I.A.
Analysis of Kigelia Africana Fruit Powder's Antioxidant and
Phytochemical Properties. *IntegrateMind: A Multidisciplinary
Journal* 2024; Vol 3, Issue 1, pp. 97-105.

Author Affiliation:

¹ Department of Animal Nutrition and Biotechnology, Ladoko
Akintola University of Technology Ogbomoso, Nigeria.

² Department of Animal Nutrition and Biochemistry, Sumitra
Research Institute, Gujarat, India. ORCID: 0000-0003-0853-6144.

Corresponding Author

²Department of Animal Nutrition and Biochemistry, Sumitra
Research Institute, Gujarat, India.

Email: dralagbe@outlook.com

Peer-Review History

Received: 21st April, 2024

Reviewed & Revised: 22/April / 2024 to 22nd May/2024

Accepted: 23rd May 2024

Published: May 2024

Peer-Review Model

External peer-review was done through double-blind method.

IntegrateMind: A Multidisciplinary Journal

ISSN: xxxx-xxxx

URL: <https://sites.google.com/view/sherwanjournals/integatemind-journal>

Ethics

No animal studies are presented in this manuscript.

No human studies are presented in this manuscript.

No potentially identifiable human images or data is presented in
this study.

License: **Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International**

Analysis of Kigelia Africana Fruit Powder's Antioxidant and Phytochemical Properties

Taiwo K. Ojediran¹, Olujimi John. A.^{*2}, Durojaye V.¹ and
Emiola, I.A.¹

ABSTRACT

This study was aimed to analyse the antioxidant and phytochemical properties of kigelia africana fruit powder. Air dried Fresh Kigelia africana fruit was milled into powdery form. Qualitative and quantitative examination showed that Kigella africana fruit powder contained saponins (35.86 mg/100g), tannins (106.1 mg/100g), phenols (1340.6 mg/100g), flavonoids (985.11 mg/100g), steroids (81.20 mg/100g), glycosides (18.32 mg/100g), triterpenes (90.65 mg/100g) and alkaloids (51.22 mg/100g). The investigation revealed that phenolic compounds had the highest concentration followed by flavonoids, tannins, triterpenes, steroids, alkaloids, saponins and glycosides. The antioxidant properties of Kigella africana fruit meal showed that it contained lipid peroxidation (71.80 %), 2, 2-diphenyl-1-picrylhydrazyl (DPPH) (56.02 %), vitamin C (6.22 %), 2, 2'-Azino -Bis- 3-Ethylbenzothiazoline -6- Sulfonic acid (ABTS) (26.11 %) and hydroxyl radical inhibition (45.92 %). Pharmacologically, the phytochemicals showed that Kigella africana fruit has antihelminthic, antidiarrheal, antimicrobial, antifungal, immunomodulatory, hypoglycemia, antioxidant, hypocholesterolemia, hepatoprotective, hepatostimulatory, analgesic and anti-carcinogenic properties. The content of lipid peroxidation, vitamin C, DPPH and ABTS in Kigella africana fruit suggests that it can be used as an antioxidant supplement in livestock diet.

Keywords: Kigelia africana fruit; Phytochemicals, Antioxidant.

1. INTRODUCTION

There is a constant need to find novel drugs and alternative treatments for illnesses and infections due to the rise in antibiotic resistance (Vera, 2021). Numerous research teams have been looking at medicinal plants for their potential antibacterial action (Vera, 2021; Alagbe, 2023). Plants used in traditional medicine contain phytochemicals or secondary metabolites, such as oxygenated terpenes, tannins, alkaloids, aldehydes, and cardiac glycosides, which are responsible for the biological properties of the plant (antioxidant, antifungal, antiviral, immunostimulatory, hepato-protective, antimicrobial, antihelminthic, and antidiarrheal activity, among others), according to Nascimento et al. (2000) and Costa et al. (2015). Numerous of these metabolites have medicinal qualities, and the primary criterion for assessing the quality and therapeutic potential of a particular herb is thought to be its concentration in the plant tissues (Wills *et al.*, 2000; Alagbe, 2021). Many natural compounds with intriguing pharmacological properties can be found in them (Edeoga *et al.*, 2005; Singh *et al.*, 2022). The Bignoniaceae family includes Kigelia africana, one of the potentially underused medicinal plants. The tree, sometimes referred to as the "sausage tree," is found across South, Central, and West Africa as well as certain regions of Asia (Maimouna et al., 2021). The plant is evergreen, with enormous, sausage-shaped, grey-green leaves that dangle on tree stalks at a length of 30 to 60 centimeters (Fagbohun et al., 2020). The gray stem bark of older trees peels off, revealing opposite or whorled leaves that are pinnately complex and up to 60 cm long (Abdulkadir et al., 2015).

SHERWAN
Publishers

Every component of the plant, including the fruit, bark, roots, and leaves, is used medicinally. For example, a decoction of the stem bark has been used to treat kidney disorders, diarrhea, cough, inflammation, renal ailments, fainting, epilepsy, rheumatism, sickle-cell anemia, psoriasis, eczema and central nervous system depression (Halder and Sharma, 2017). Leaves and stem bark have been used for treating dysentery, constipation, fevers, and as an abortifacient. Leaves are also used to prepare a tonic for improved health and growth (Owolabi and Omogba, 2007). The fruit, edible by several mammalian species, contains flavonoids, terpenes, tannins, steroids, saponins and caffeic acid (Halder and Sharma, 2017). Furthermore, it was shown that a methanolic extract of *Kigelia africana* inhibited the growth of *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, *Salmonella Typhi*, *Bacillus subtilis*, *Klebsiella pneumoniae* and other pathogenic organisms (Picerno *et al.*, 2005; Weiss *et al.*, 2000). Some medicinal plants contain a variety of phytochemicals that can have high antioxidant activity. Compounds that are accountable for reducing oxidative stress could be extracted from plants and then used for the development of drugs for the better management of several metabolic diseases in livestock (Alagbe, 2024). Evaluation of chemical compounds in these plants particularly *Kigelia africana* will also help to reduce the increasing cases of antimicrobial resistance, reduce environmental pollution, and promote food safety.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1. Experimental laboratory

The study was carried out at the laboratory Unit of the Department of Animal Nutrition and Biotechnology, Ladoke Akintola University of Technology Ogbomosho, Oyo State, located in the derived savannah area, latitude (8° 08'N) and longitude (4° 15'E) at an altitude of 347 meters (Ojediran *et al.*, 2021).

2.2. Sample preparation and processing

Fresh *Kigelia africana* fruit was harvested from within Ladoke Akintola University Teaching and Research Farm, Ogbomosho, and transferred to the Department of Biological Sciences of the same institution where it was identified and authenticated by a certified taxonomist and assigned a voucher specimen number TT/008A/2023. Harvested fruit was sliced into smaller fractions and air-dried for 14 days until a constant weight was obtained. Dried fruit was milled with an electrical blender into powder, kept in a labeled air-tight polythene bag, and taken to the laboratory for further examination. 00 g of *Kigelia africana* fruit powder was weighed into a conical flask containing 1000 mL water and kept for 4 days during which it was stirred intermittently after every 4 hours. The mixture was thereafter filtered through a Whatman filter paper. The extract was evaporated into dryness in a rotary evaporator under reduced pressure at 50°C to obtain *Kigelia africana* fruit extract (CSE).

2.3. Qualitative phytochemical screening of *Kigelia africana* fruit extract

Phytochemical analysis extract was carried out using the method described by Odebiyi and Sofowora (1978) for the detection of saponins, tannins, phenolics, alkaloids, steroids, triterpenes, phlobatannins, glycosides and flavonoids.

1. Alkaloids: 1cm³ of 1%HCl was added to 3cm³ of the extracts in a test tube. The mixture was heated for 20 minutes, cooled and filtered. The filtrate was used in the following tests: 2 drops of Wagner's reagent was added to 1cm³ of the extracts. A reddish brown precipitate indicates the presence of alkaloids
2. Tannins: 1cm³ of freshly prepared 10% KOH was added to 1cm³ of the extracts. A dirty white precipitate indicates the presence of tannins.
3. Phenolics: 2 drops of 5% FeCl₃ was added to 1cm³ of the extracts in a test tube. A greenish precipitate indicates the presence of phenolics.
4. Glycosides: 10cm³ of 50% H₂SO₄ was added to 1cm³ of the extracts, and the mixture was heated in boiling water for 15 minutes. 10cm³ of Fehling's solution was added and the mixture boiled. A brick-red precipitate indicates the presence of glycosides.
5. Saponins: Frothing test: 2cm³ of the extract in a test tube was vigorously shaken for 2 minutes. Frothing indicates the presence of saponins.
6. Flavonoids: 1cm³ of 10% NaOH was added to 3cm³ of the extracts. A yellow colouration indicates the presence of flavonoids.
7. Steroids: salakowsti test: 5 drops of concentrated H₂SO₄ was added to 1cm³ of the extracts. Red colouration indicates the presence of steroids
8. Phlobatannins: 1cm³ of the extracts was added to 1% HCl. A red precipitate indicates the presence of phlobatannins.
9. Triterpenes: 5 drops of acetic anhydride were added to 1cm³ of the extracts. A drop of concentrated H₂SO₄ was then added and the mixture was steamed for 1 hour and neutralized with NaOH followed by the addition of chloroform. A blue-green colour indicates the presence of triterpenes.

10. Phytosterols (Finar 1986): liberman-burchard's test: 50mg is dissolved in 2ml acetic anhydride. To this, one or two drops of con. H₂SO₄ was added slowly along the sides of the test tube. An array of colour changes shows the presence of phytosterols.
11. Terpenoids: 5ml of aqueous extract of the sample is mixed with 2ml of CHCl₃ in a test tube 3ml of con. H₂SO₄ is carefully added to the mixture to form a layer. An interface with a reddish-brown coloration is formed if terpenoid constituent is present.
12. Determination of Coumarin: Add 0.5 ml of 5N NaOH to the solution for 1 ml of the extract (0.5 g in 1ml of ethanol), heat at 80 °C for 5 min, cool, add 0.75 ml of 5 N H₂SO₄, mix thoroughly, add 0.25 g of anhydrous NaHCO₃, mix, and transfer to the extractor.

Rinse the flask with distilled water and transfer to the extractor and make up to 50 ml. extract for 3 hrs with pet. Ether, removes the inner tube and transfers the pet ether in the extractor to the extraction flask. Add 20 ml of water to the pet ether extract and carefully evaporate the pet ether in a water bath at 50-55 °C. Transfer the aqueous solution to a volumetric flask, making up to 50 ml with continuous mixing. pipette 25 ml into a flask and add 1% Na₂CO₃ solution, heat in a water bath at 85 °C for 15 min and cool. Add 5 ml of the diazonium solution, and let stand for 2 hours. Read the absorbance at 540 nm against the reagent blank. Calculate the coumarin content from a standard curve.

3. METHODS OF ANALYSIS

3.1. Quantitative analysis of *Kigelia africana* fruit extract

3.1.1. Estimation of total phenolic content

The total phenolic content of the sample was estimated according to the method of Makkar *et al.* (1997). The aliquots of the extract were taken in a test tube and made up to the volume of 1 ml with distilled water. Then 0.5ml of Folin-Ciocalteu reagent (1:1 with water) and 2.5 ml of sodium carbonate solution (20%) were added sequentially to the test tube. Soon after vortexing the reaction mixture, the tubes were placed in the dark for 40 min. and the absorbance was recorded at 725 nm against the reagent blank. Using Gallic acid monohydrate, a standard curve was prepared. The linearity obtained was in the range of 1-10 µg/ml. using the standard curve, the total phenolic content was calculated and expressed as Gallic acid equivalent in mg/g of extract.

3.1.2. Total flavonoid assay

Total flavonoid content was measured by aluminium chloride colorimetric assay outlined by Tolari *et al.* (2012). 1ml of extracts or standard solution of Quercetin (500µg/ml) was added to 10 ml volumetric flask containing 4 ml of distilled water. To the above mixture, 0.3 ml of 5% NaNO₂ was added. After 5 minutes, 0.3 ml of 10% AlCl₃ was added. At 6th min, 2 ml of 1 M NaOH was added and the total volume was made up to 10 ml with distilled water. The solution was mixed well and the absorbance was measured against the prepared reagent blank at 510 nm. The total flavonoid content of the flower was expressed as a percentage of Quercetin equivalent per 100 g of fresh mass.

3.2. Estimation of Saponins

The spectrophotometric method of Madhu *et al.* (2016) was used for the analysis of saponins. Briefly, 1g of the finely ground dried sample was weighed into a 250ml beaker, and 100ml of isobutyl alcohol was added. The mixture was shaken on a UDY shaker for 5 hours to ensure uniform mixing. Thereafter, the mixture was filtered through a Whatman No. 1 filter paper into a 100ml beaker containing 20ml of 40% saturated solution of MgCO₃. The resulting mixture was again filtered to obtain a clear colourless solution. One millilitre of the colourless filtrate was pipette into a 50ml volumetric flask and 2ml of 5% FeCl₃ solution was added and made up to the marked level with distilled water. This was then allowed to stand for 30 minutes for a blood-red colour to develop. 0-10ppm saponins standard was prepared from saponins stock solution. The standard solutions were treated similarly with 2ml of 5% FeCl₃ solution as earlier described. The absorbance of the samples as well as standard saponin solutions was read after colour development using a Jenway V6300 spectrophotometer at a wavelength of 380nm. Percentage saponin was calculated using the formula:

$$\% \text{ saponin} = \frac{\text{Absorbance of sample} \times \text{Average gradient} \times \text{Dilution factor}}{\text{Weight of sample} \times 10,000}$$

3.3. Alkaloids content estimation

The quantitative determination of alkaloids was done by distillation and titrimetric methods as described by Madhu (2016). Briefly, 2g of finely ground sample was weighed into a 100ml beaker, and 20mls of 80% absolute alcohol was added to give a smooth paste. The mixture was transferred to a 250ml flask and more alcohol added to make up to 1g of magnesium oxide was then added. The mixture was digested in a boiling water bath for an hour and half under a reflux air condenser with occasional shaking. The mixture was filtered while hot through a Buchner funnel. The residue was poured back into the flask and re-digested for another thirty minutes with 50ml alcohol after which the alcohol was evaporated. Distilled water was added to replace the lost alcohol. When all

alcohol has evaporated, 3 drops of 10% HCl was added. The whole solution was later transferred into a 250ml volumetric flask; 5ml of Zinc acetate solution and 5ml of potassium ferricyanide solution were thoroughly mixed to give a homogenous mixture. The flask was allowed to stand for a few minutes, filtered through a dry filter paper, and 10ml of the filtrate was transferred into a separating funnel and the alkaloids present were extracted vigorously by shaking with five successive portions of chloroform. The residue obtained was dissolved in 10ml of hot distilled water and transferred into a Kjeldahl tube with the addition of 0.2g of selenium for digestion to a clear colourless solution. The clear colourless solution was used to determine Nitrogen using Kjeldahl distillation apparatus the distillate was back titrated with 0.01N HCl and the titre value obtained was used to calculate the % Nitrogen using the formulae:

$$\%N = \frac{\text{Titre value} \times \text{Atomic mass of Nitrogen} \times \text{Normality of HCl} \times 100}{\text{Weight of sample (mg)}}$$

$$\% \text{ Alkaloid} = \% \text{ Nitrogen} \times 3.26$$

Where 3.26 is a constant

3.4. Tannins analysis

The method of Madhu *et al* (2016) was used to determine the quantity of tannins. 0.20g of sample was measured into a 50ml beaker 20ml of 50% methanol was added and covered with parafilm and placed in a water bath at 77-80°C for 1 hour. It was shaken thoroughly to ensure uniform mixing. The extract was filtered using a double-layered Whatman No. 41-filter paper into a 100ml volumetric flask. 20ml water was added and 2.5ml Folin-Denis reagent and 10ml of 17% Na₂CO₃ were added and mixed properly. The mixture was made up to mark with water mixed well and allowed to stand for 20 minutes. A bluish-green colour will develop at the end of the range. 0-10ppm was treated similarly as 1ml sample above. The absorbances of the Tannic acid standard solutions as well as samples were read after colour development on a spectronic 21D spectrophotometer at a wavelength of 760nm. % Tannin was calculated using the formula:

$$\% \text{ Tannin} = \frac{\text{Absorbance of sample} \times \text{Average gradient} \times \text{Dilution factor}}{\text{Weight of sample} \times 10,000}$$

3.5. Glycosides estimation

10ml of the extract was pipette into a 250ml conical flask. 50ml Chloroform was added and shaken on a Vortex Mixer for 1 hour. The mixture was filtered into a conical flask. 10ml pyridine and 2ml of 2% sodium nitroprusside were added and shaken thoroughly for 10 minutes. 3ml of 20% NaOH was later added to develop a brownish-yellow colour. The Glycoside standard of concentration ranging from 0-5mg/ml was prepared from 100mg/ml stock glycoside standard. The series of standards 0-5mg/ml was treated similarly like the sample above. The absorbances of the sample as well as standards were read on a spectronic 21D Digital spectrophotometer at a wavelength of 510nm. % Glycoside was calculated using the formula:

$$\% \text{ Glycoside} = \frac{\text{Absorbance of sample} \times \text{Average gradient} \times \text{Dilution factor}}{\text{Weight of sample} \times 10,000}$$

3.6. Analysis of steroids

0.05g of sample the extract was weighed into a 100ml beaker. 20ml of chloroform-methanol (2:1) mixture was added to dissolve the extract upon shaking for 30 minutes on a shaker. The whole mixture until free of steroids. 1ml of the filtrate was pipette into a 30ml test tube and 5ml of alcoholic KOH was added and shaken thoroughly to obtain a homogenous mixture. The mixture was later placed in a water bath set at 37°C-40°C for 90 minutes. It was cooled to room temperature and 10ml of petroleum ether was added followed by the addition of 5ml distilled water. This was evaporated to dryness on the water bath. 6ml of Liebermann Buchard reagent was added to the residue in a dry bottle and absorbance was taken at a wavelength of 620nm on a spectronic 21D digital spectrophotometer. Standard steroids of concentration of 0-4mg/ml were prepared from 100mg/ml stock steroid solution and treated similarly like the sample as above.

% steroid was calculated using the formula:

$$\% \text{ steroid} = \frac{\text{Absorbance of sample} \times \text{Average gradient} \times \text{Dilution factor}}{\text{Weight of sample} \times 10,000}$$

3.7. Triterpenes estimation

0.50g of sample was weighed into a 50ml conical flask and 20ml of 2:1 chloroform-methanol mixture was added, shaken thoroughly, and allowed to stand for 15 minutes. The supernatant obtained was discarded, and the precipitate was re-washed with another 20ml chloroform-methanol mixture for re-centrifugation. The resultant precipitate was dissolved in 40ml of 10% Sodium Dodecyl Sulphate (SDS) solution. 1ml of 0.01M ferric chloride solution was added to the above at 30-second intervals; shaken well,

and allowed to stand for 30 minutes. Standard triterpenes of concentration range 0-5mg/ml were prepared from 100mg/l stock triterpenes solution from Sigma-Aldrich chemicals, U.S.A. The absorbance of the sample as well as that of standard concentrations of triterpenes was read on a digital spectrophotometer at a wavelength of 510nm.

The percentage of triterpenes was calculated using the formula:

$$= \frac{\text{Absorbance of sample} \times \text{Average gradient} \times \text{Dilution factor}}{\text{Weight of sample} \times 10,000}$$

3.8. Determination of Antioxidant Properties of *Kigelia africana* fruit extract

3.8.1. DPPH assay

Evaluation of DPPH radical scavenging method was adopted as reported by Chandra and Goyal (2014). Free radical scavenging activity of the extract was measured by 2, 2-diphenyl-1-picrylhydrazyl (DPPH). Here 0.1 mM solution of DPPH in ethanol was prepared and added to 3 ml of the extracts. The mixture was then shaken vigorously and allowed to stand at room temperature for 30 minutes. The absorbance was then measured at 520 nm using a spectrophotometer. The percentage DPPH scavenging effect was calculated by using the following equation:

Percentage inhibition % = Absorbance of control reaction minus absorbance in the presence of test or standard sample divided by Absorbance of control reaction all multiplied by 100

3.8.2. Vitamin C analysis

The vitamin C content of the *Kigelia africana* fruit extract was analysed according to the methods outlined by (Benderitter *et al.*, 1998). 2 g dinitrophenyl hydrazine with 270 mg copper sulfate and 230 mg thiourea in 100 ml of 5 ml/L H₂SO₄ was added to 300 µl of an adequate dilution of *Kigelia africana* fruit extract with 100 µl of 13.3% (v/v) trichloroacetic acid and water. The reaction mixture was then incubated at 37 °C for 3 hours before adding 0.5 ml of sulphuric acid to the medium and measuring the absorbance at 520 nm with a spectrophotometer.

3.8.3. Lipid peroxidation inhibition

The analysis was carried out according to the method outlined by Oloruntola *et al.* (2022). 2 ml of *Kigelia africana* fruit extract was added to 1 mL iron (III) chloride, 50 µL of bovine brain phospholipids, 1mM ascorbic acid in 20 mM phosphate buffer. It was incubated at 37°C for 1 hour and the spectrophotometer was set at an optical density of 456 nm to determine lipid peroxidation inhibition assay.

3.8.4. 2, 2'-Azino -Bis- 3- Ethylbenzothiazoline -6- Sulfonic acid (ABTS) assay

2 mL of *Kigelia africana* fruit extract was added to 1 mL of 2, 2'-Azino -Bis- 3- Ethylbenzothiazoline -6- Sulfonic acid and mixed. Absorbance was assessed after 30 minutes at different concentrations (10, 20, 30, 40 and 50 mg/ml). The radical scavenging percentage was determined with a blank that had no scavenger following methods outlined by Turkoglu *et al.* (2010).

3.8.5. Hydroxyl radical inhibition

Hydroxyl radical inhibition assay was ascertained according to the procedure outlined by Tijani *et al.* (2012). 2mL of *Kigelia africana* fruit extract was mixed with deoxyribose, hydrogen peroxide, and ascorbic acid at 3.0 mM, 0.1 mM, and 0.2 mM respectively. The mixture was incubated at 37°C for 60 minutes and the spectrophotometer was set at an optical density of 625 nm to determine hydroxyl inhibition assay.

3.9. Statistical analysis

All analysis was carried out in triplicates and results obtained were expressed as the mean value ± standard deviation.

4. FINDINGS AND DISCUSSION

Table 1 and 2 reveals the qualitative and quantitative composition of *Kigella africana* fruit powder. The sample contained saponins (35.86 mg/100g), tannins (106.1 mg/100g), phenols (1340.6 mg/100g), flavonoids (985.11 mg/100g), steroids (81.20 mg/100g), glycosides (18.32 mg/100g), triterpenes (90.65 mg/100g) and alkaloids (51.22 mg/100g). The investigation revealed that phenolic compounds had the highest concentration followed by flavonoids, tannins, triterpenes, steroids, alkaloids, saponins and glycosides. Earlier studies have reported 398.7 mg/100g, 35.17 mg/100g, 171 mg/100g and 0.61 mg/100g for flavonoids, tannins, anthocyanins, and phenols of *Kigella pinnata* fruit (Khaled *et al.*, 2022). However, the result obtained aligns with the reports of Fitriyani (2018). The discrepancies in their outcome can be attributed to variations in species, age of the plant, and geographical location amongst others (Singh *et al.*, 2022). The leaf of *Kigella africana* fruit is reported to have different beneficial pharmacological effects, with many variant mechanisms of action such as: antimicrobial, antifungal, immunomodulatory, hypoglycemia, antioxidant, hypocholesterolemia, hepatoprotective, hepatostimulatory properties amongst others (Alagbe, 2022; Adewale *et al.*, 2021).

Table 1: Result on qualitative analysis of *Kigella africana* fruit powder

Phytochemicals Status	
Saponins	+
Tannins	+
Phenols	+++
Steroids	+
Coumarin	+
Flavoniods	++
Glycosides	+
Terpenoids	+
Triterpenes	-
Anthocyanin	-
Phlobatanin	-
Amino acids	-
Alkaloids	+

Note: + Present; ++ Moderately present; +++ Highly present; - Absent

The beneficial effects *Kigella africana* fruit come from one or more types of phyto-constituents or bioactive compounds, often acting synergistically (Musa et al., 2021; Wills et al., 2000). These chemically distinct, but often overlapping, classes of phyto-constituents are mainly terpenoids (such as sesquiterpenes and saponins), phenols (such as tannins) and their glycosides (flavonoids, glucosinolates) (Alagbe, 2024; Singh et al., 2022). They are also widely used in the food, pharmaceutical and cosmetic industries (Wilasrusmee et al., 2002). Saponins are a heterogenous group of water soluble triterpenoids which are widely distributed in the plant kingdom, (Macrae et al., 1993) and are known for their bitter, astringent taste (Cowan, 1999; Daniel and Alagbe, 2023). They have also been suggested possess antidiarrheal properties and are useful in the treatment of respiratory diseases (Shittu et al., 2021; Davendran and Balasubramanian, 2011). Tannins exhibit antimicrobial, anti-inflammatory and immune-stimulatory properties (Simlai and Roy, 2012). Excessive dietary intake of tannins can interfere with the calcium and iron absorption in the body (Edeoga et al., 2015). Flavonoids have attracted interest as possible antioxidants both for inhibiting oxidative deterioration of foodstuffs (Rauha et al., 2000) and for providing beneficial metabolic effects in animals (Harris et al., 2001; Alagbe, 2022). Phenols are strong antioxidants that are capable of scavenging free radicals which are the major cause of diseases or infections in animals (Mamza et al., 2012). Steroids, terpenoids and steroids show many pharmacological activities, such as antibacterial, antiviral, anti-inflammatory, antifungal, antioxidant, analgesic (painkiller) and anti-carcinogenic properties (Gupta et al., 1999).

Table 2: Quantitative analysis on the phytochemicals in *Kigella africana* fruit powder

Parameters	Composition (mg/100g)
Saponins	35.86± 2.07
Tannins	106.1± 1.55
Phenols	1340.6 ± 0.99
Flavonoids	985.11±0.17
Steroids	81.20±0.00
Glycosides	18.32±0.10
Triterpenes	90.65±1.16
Alkaloids	51.22±0.09

Source: Author's estimate.

The antioxidant properties of *Kigella africana* fruit is presented in Table 3. The sample contained lipid peroxidation (71.80 %), 2, 2-diphenyl-1-picrylhydrazyl (DPPH) (56.02 %), vitamin C (6.22 %), 2, 2'-Azino -Bis- 3- Ethylbenzothiazoline -6- Sulfonic acid (ABTS) (26.11 %) and hydroxyl radical inhibition (45.92 %). The content of lipid peroxidation, vitamin C, DPPH and ABTS in *Kigella africana* fruit suggests that it can be used as an antioxidant supplement in livestock diet (Atolani et al., 2011). Antioxidants are compounds that can delay or inhibit the oxidation of lipids or other molecules by inhibiting oxidising chain reactions. The antioxidant activity of phenolic compounds is mainly due to their redox properties which play an important role in neutralising free radicals and decomposing peroxides (Zheleva, 2012). Dietary antioxidants have been defined as any substance that when present in low concentrations than that of the oxidizable substrate, significantly delays or inhibits the oxidation of that substrate (Halliwell, 2007). Mohammed et al. (2013) stated that the total phenolic content in the plant extract is linked to antioxidant capacity, which is

also a function of the structures of phenolic compounds.

Table 3: Antioxidant composition of *Kigella africana* fruit powder

Parameters	Composition
2, 2-diphenyl-1-picrylhydrazyl (DPPH) (%)	56.02±0.01
Lipid peroxidation (%)	71.80±0.00
Vitamin C (mg/g)	6.22±0.00
¹ ABTS (%)	26.11±0.02
Hydroxyl radical inhibition (%)	45.92±0.04

Source: '2, 2'-Azino -Bis- 3- Ethylbenzothiazoline -6- Sulfonic acid.

Basically, phenolic antioxidants (PPH) inhibit lipid peroxidation through a rapid donation of the hydrogen atom to the peroxy radical (ROO) which results in the formation of alkyl (aryl) hydroperoxide (ROOH). Vitamin C is essential because it has the ability to scavenge radicals, which neutralizes the damaging effects of lipid peroxidation and DNA damage caused by free radicals (Oloruntola and Ayodeji, 2022). Additionally, they can strengthen the defenses of cells against oxidative damage (Dudonnd et al., 2009). Antioxidants obtained from plants have been associated with a lower risk of degenerative illnesses such as cancer, coronary atherosclerosis, and Alzheimer's disease (Oloruntola, 2021; Biswas et al., 2020).

5. CONCLUSIONS

The presence phytochemicals such as phenolic compounds, flavonoids, tannins, triterpenes, steroids, alkaloids, saponins and glycosides showed that *Kigella africana* fruit has antihelminthic, antidiarrheal, antimicrobial, antifungal, immunomodulatory, hypoglycemia, antioxidant, hypocholesterolemia, hepatoprotective, hepatostimulatory, analgesic and anti-carcinogenic properties. The content of lipid peroxidation, vitamin C, DPPH and ABTS in *Kigella africana* fruit suggests that it can be used as an antioxidant supplement in livestock diet.

Ethical approval

All international standards have been adopted and compliance.

Informed consent

The study was conducted with equal participation by all authors.

Conflicts of interests

The authors declare that there are no conflicts of interests.

Funding

The study has not received any external funding.

Data and materials availability

All data associated with this study are present in the paper.

REFERENCES AND NOTES

1. Abdulkadir, M. N., Adedokun, A., & John, E. (2015). Phytochemical composition and antimicrobial evaluation of *Kigelia africana* LAM. *Asian Journal of Plant Science and Research*, 5, 14-17.
2. Adewale, A. O., Alagbe, J. O., & Adeoye, A. O. (2021). Dietary supplementation of *Rauvolfia vomitoria* root extract as a phyto-genic feed additive in growing rabbit diets: Haematology and serum biochemical indices. *International Journal of Orange Technologies*, 3(3), 1-12.
3. Alagbe, J. O. (2021). Dietary supplementation of *Rauvolfia vomitoria* root extract as a phyto-genic feed additive in growing rabbit diets: Growth performance and caecal microbial population. *Concept in Dairy and Veterinary Sciences*, 4(2), 2021.
4. Alagbe, J. O. (2022). Use of medicinal plants as a panacea to poultry production and food security: A review. *Gospodarka I Innowacje*, 22(2022), 1-12.
5. Alagbe, J. O. (2023). Bioactive compounds in ethanolic extract of *Strychnos innocua* root using gas chromatography and mass spectrometry (GC-MS). *Drug Discovery*, 17, e4dd1005.
6. Alagbe, J. O., Adeyemi, S. O., Akpan, E., Adeosun, C. B., & Olatunji, G. A. (2011). Chemical composition and antioxidant potentials of *Kigelia pinnata* root oil and extracts. *Excli Journal*, 10, 264-273.
7. Alagbe, J. O., Bamigboye, S., Nwosu, G. C., Agbonika, D. A., & Kadiri, M. C. (2023). Characterization of bioactive compounds in *Luffa aegyptiaca* leaf ethanolic extracts using gas chromatography and mass spectrometry (GC-MS). *Drug Discovery*, 17, e10dd1011.
8. Alagbe, J. O., Kadiri, M. C., Oluwafemi, R. A., Agubosi, O. C. P., & Anorue, D. N. (2023). Analysis of bioactive compounds in ethanolic extracts of *Xylopiya aethiopyca* leaves using gas chromatography and mass spectrometry technique. *American Journal of Science on Integration and Human Development*, 1(1), 1-10.
9. Alagbe, J. O., Shittu, M. D., & Tanimomo, B. K. (2022). Influence of *Anogeissus leiocarpus* stem bark on the fatty acid composition in meat of broiler chickens. *European Journal of Life Safety and Stability*, 14(22), 13-22.
10. Alagbe, J. O., Shittu, M. D., & Ushie, F. T. (2021). GC-MS analysis of methanolic stem bark extract of *Zollingeriana indigofera*. *Asian Journal of Advances in Research*, 11(4), 144-146.
11. Alagbe, O. J., Agubosi, O. C. P., & Oluwafemi, R. A. (2023). Histopathology of broiler chickens fed diet supplemented with *Prosopis africana* (African mesquite) essential oil. *Brazilian Journal of Science*, 2(9), 49-59.
12. Alagbe, O. J., Agubosi, O. C. P., Oluwafemi, R. A., Akande, T. O., Adegbite, E. A., & Emiola, I. A. (2023). Haemato-biochemical indices and intestinal microbial population of broiler chickens fed diet supplemented with *Prosopis africana* (African mesquite) essential oil. *Brazilian Journal of Science*, 2(9), 98-110.
13. Alagbe, O. J., Muhammad, R. S., Shittu, M. D., & Olagoke, O. C. (2022). Effect of *Trichilia monadelpha* stem bark extract on the fatty acid composition of rabbit's thigh meat. *Journal of Environmental Issues and Climate Change*, 1(1), 63-71.
14. Alagbe, O. J., & Oluwafemi, R. A. (2023). Sensory evaluation and fatty acid composition of broiler chickens fed diets containing *Prosopis africana* oil. *Journal of Healthcare and Biomedical Science*, 1(2), 36-45.
15. Atolani, O., Adeyemi, S. O., Akpan, E., Adeosun, C. B., & Olatunji, G. A. (2011). Chemical composition and antioxidant potentials of *Kigelia pinnata* root oil and extracts. *Excli Journal*, 10, 264-273.
16. Benderitter, M., Maupoli, V., Vergely, C., Dalloz, F., Briot, F., & Rochette, L. (1998). Studies by electron paramagnetic resonance of the importance of iron in the hydroxyl scavenging properties of ascorbic acid in plasma: Effects of iron chelators. *Fundamental and Clinical Pharmacology*, 12(5), 510-516.
17. Biswas, A., Dey, S., Li, D., Yiu, L., Zhang, J., & Huang, S. (2020). Comparison of phytochemical profile, mineral content, and in vitro antioxidant activities of *Corchorus capsularis* and *Corchorus olitorius* leaf extracts from different populations. *Journal of Food Quality*, 2020, 2931097.
18. Chandra, S., & Goyal, A. T. (2014). Antioxidant activity by DPPH radical scavenging method of *Ageratum conyzoides* Linn. leaves. *American Journal of Ethnomedicine*, 1(4), 244-249.
19. Cowan, M. M. (1999). Plant products as antimicrobial agents. *Clinical Microbiology Reviews*, 12, 564-582.
20. Dudonné, S., Vitrac, X., Coutière, P., Woillez, M., & Mérillon, J. (2009). Comparative study of antioxidant properties and total phenolic content of 30 plant extracts of industrial interest using DPPH, ABTS, FRAP, SOD, and ORAC assays. *Journal of Agricultural and Food Chemistry*, 57, 1768-1774.
21. Fagbohun, O. F., Babalola, O. O., Agboola, F. K., Joseph, J. S., Malindisa, S., & Msagati, T. A. M. (2020). Evaluation of phytochemicals, antioxidants, trace elements in *Kigelia africana* fruit extracts and chemical profiling analysis using UHPLC-qTOF-MS2 spectrometry. *Biological Trace Element Research*, 195, 679-695.
22. Gupta, O. P., Singh, S., Bani, S., Sharma, N., Malhotra, S., Gupta, B. D., Banerjee, S. K., & Handa, S. S. (1999). Anti-inflammatory and anti-arthritis activities of silymarin acting through inhibition of 5-lipoxygenase. *Phytomedicine*, 7, 21-24.
23. Halliwell, B. (2007). Biochemistry of oxidative stress. *Biochemical Society Transactions*, 35(5), 1147-1150.
24. Halder, S., & Sharma, A. (2017). A review on *Kigelia Africana*. *World Journal of Pharmaceutical Research*, 6, 389-411.
25. Harris, J. C., Cottrell, S. L., Plummer, S., & Lloyd, D. (2001). Antimicrobial properties of *Allium sativum* (garlic). *Applied Microbiology and Biotechnology*, 57, 282-286.
26. Khaled, M. A., Hossam, S. E., Heba, I. M., Tarek, A. S., Ahmed, G., Abdallah, T. M., Mohammed, A. A., & Falam, S. A. (2022). Antioxidant, anticancer activity, and phytochemical profiling of *Kigelia pinnata* fruits. *Separations*, 9(11), 379-388.
27. Macrae, R., Robinson, R. K., & Sadler, M. J. (1993). *Encyclopaedia of food science, food technology and nutrition*. London: Academic Press.
28. Makkar, H. P. S., Norsambu, T., Lkhavatsere, S., & Becker, K. (2009). Plant secondary metabolites in some medical plants of Mongolia used for enhancing animal health and production. *Tropicultura*, 27(3), 159-167.
29. Madhu, M., Sailaja, V., Satyadev, T. N. V. S., & Satyanarayana, M. V. (2016). Quantitative phytochemical analysis of selected medicinal plant species using various organic solvents. *Journal of Pharmacognosy and Phytochemistry*, 5(2), 25-29.
30. Mohammed, H. A., Alshalmani, S. K., & Abdellatif, A. G. (2013).

- Antioxidant and quantitative estimation of phenolic and flavonoids of three halophytic plants growing in Libya. *Journal of Pharmacognosy and Phytochemistry*, 2(3), 89-94.
31. Muritala, D. S., Alagbe, J. O., Ojebiyi, O. O., Ojediran, T. K., & Rafiu, T. A. (2022). Growth performance and haematological and serum biochemical parameters of broiler chickens given varied concentrations of *Polyalthia longifolia* leaf extract in place of conventional antibiotics. *Animal Science and Genetics*, 18(2), 57-71.
32. Oloruntola, O. D. (2021). Proximate, phytochemical, mineral composition and antioxidant activity of *Anacardium occidentale* L. leaf powder. *Dysona Life Science*, 2, 39-49.
33. Oloruntola, O. D., & Ayodele, S. O. (2022). Phytochemical, proximate and mineral composition, antioxidant and antidiabetic properties evaluation and comparison of mistletoe leaves from moringa and kolanut trees. *Turkish Journal of Agriculture-Food Science and Technology*, 10(8), 1524-1531.
34. Oloruntola, O. D., Ayodele, S. O., Adeyeye, S. A., Fasuhami, O. S., Osowe, C. O., & Ganiyu, T. (2022). Proximate composition, phytochemical profile, antioxidant, antidiabetic, and anti-inflammatory properties of *Justica carnea* leaf powder. *Black Sea Journal of Agriculture*, 5(4), 415-423.
35. Owolabi, O. J., & Omogbai, E. K. I. (2007). Analgesic and anti-inflammatory activities of the ethanolic stem bark extract of *Kigelia africana* (Bignoniaceae). *African Journal of Biotechnology*, 6, 582-585.
36. Picerno, P., Autore, G., Marzocco, S., Meloni, M., Sanogo, R., & Aquino, R. P. (2005). Anti-inflammatory activity of verminoside from *Kigelia africana* and evaluation of cutaneous irritation in cell cultures and reconstituted human epidermis. *Journal of Natural Products*, 68, 1610-1614.
37. Rauha, J. P., Remes, S., Heinonen, M., Hopia, A., Kahkonen, M., Kujala, T., Pihlaja, K., Vuorela, H., & Vuorela, P. (2000). Antimicrobial effects of Finnish plant extracts containing flavonoids and other phenolic compounds. *International Journal of Food Microbiology*, 56, 3-12.
38. Singh, S., Alagbe, O. J., Liu, X., Sharma, R., & Kumar, A. (2022). Comparative analysis of ethanolic *Juniperus thurifera* leaf, stem bark and root extract using gas chromatography and mass spectrometry. *International Journal of Agriculture and Animal Production*, 2(6), 18-27.
39. Talari, S., Rudroju, S., Penchala, S., & Nanna Rama, S. (2012). Quantification of total phenolics and total flavonoid contents in extracts of *Oroxylum indicum* I. Kurz. *Asian Journal of Pharmaceutical and Clinical Research*, 5(4), 177-179.
40. Turkoglu, S., Celik, S., Turkoglu, I., Cakilcioglu, U., & Bahsi, M. (2010). Determination of the antioxidant properties of ethanol and water extracts from different parts of *Teucrium parviflorum* Schreber. *African Journal of Biotechnology*, 9(40), 6797-6805.
41. Vera, B. (2021). Essential oils knowledge: From facts to farm or from farm to facts. *International Poultry Magazine*, 3(3), 2-4.
42. Weiss, C. R., Moideen, S. V., Croft, S. L., & Houghton, P. J. (2000). Activity of extracts and isolated naphthoquinones from *Kigelia pinnata* against *Plasmodium falciparum*. *Journal of Natural Products*, 63, 1306-1309.
43. Wilasrusmee, C., Kittur, S., Shah, G., Siddiqui, J., Bruch, D., Wilasrusmee, S., & Kittur, D. S. (2002). Immunostimulatory effect of *Silybum marianum* (milk thistle) extract. *Medical Science Monitor*, 8, BR439-BR443.
44. Wills, R. B. H., Bone, K., & Morgan, M. (2000). Herbal products: Active constituents, modes of action and quality control. *Nutrition Research Reviews*, 13, 47-77.
45. Zheleva, A. (2012). *Electron paramagnetic resonance-oxidative status and antioxidant activity*. Trakia University: Academic Press, Stara Zagora, Bulgaria.

Disclaimer/Publisher's Note: The statements, opinions and data contained in all publications are solely those of the individual author(s) and contributor(s) and not of Sherwan Journals and/or the editor(s). Sherwan Journals and/or the editor(s) disclaim responsibility for any injury to people or property resulting from any ideas, methods, instructions or products referred to in the content.